

Lack of Interest in Reading Can Have a Negative Impact on Academic Achievement

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ABSTRACT

Interest in reading is an urge to understand word for word and the content contained in the reading text, so that readers can understand the things stated in the reading. Lack of interest in reading among students, especially university students. Even though reading will influence thinking patterns, the scope of learning activities in college is wider and deeper than studying at previous schools. Of course this will affect academic achievement. By collecting data by studying several related theories. And the result is that students' low interest in reading will cause a decrease in their ability to think, work, be passive, and play a less active role in learning so that their academic achievements are also less.

INTRODUCTION

Education is the main key to all quality progress and development, because with education humans can realize all the good potential within themselves. And in the process of gaining knowledge in the world of education, reading is an important factor in this process. As stated by Darmadi (2018), reading is a process carried out and used by humans to obtain messages conveyed by writers through the medium of written language. Another definition of reading is a process of matching letters or reciting written language symbols. And according to Nurwati (2011) Reading is the gateway to science, which has an important role in increasing broad insight and knowledge and in turn being motivated to put forward one's own ideas based on experience gained through reading activities, in this case schools have a strategic role in developing abilities, interests and passion for reading to improve students' learning achievements.

But in this era where everything is in the digital phase, there are more people who have no interest at all in reading. Taringan (2014) argues that interest in reading is a person's ability to communicate with oneself to capture the meaning contained in writing so as to provide an emotional experience resulting from a form of deep attention to the meaning of reading. The influence of technology, in this case social media, is one of the factors that makes a person's interest in reading, in this case students, very less.

In fact, the fact stated by Taringan (2014) is that if students read without having a high interest in reading, they will not read wholeheartedly. So that students can know the meaning reading requires a high interest in reading. Students' reading interest can be seen by the students' habit of reading. If you are used to reading, this habit will be carried out regularly. Apart from that, the love of reading has a good impact on students. If students read regularly, their ability to understand the meaning of reading will be good.

Interest in reading in Indonesia is still very low compared to interest in other countries. As stated by Prabandari (2006), interest in reading is still a problem because there is a phenomenon that shows the low interest in reading among Indonesian people. When compared with other countries in the world, interest in reading in Indonesia is still relatively low. In Asia alone, Indonesia's reading interest still lags behind neighboring countries such as Singapore and Malaysia. The problem of low interest in reading does not only occur among the general public, but this also occurs among students and even students. Even though we all know that an interest in reading is very important for a student, in order to achieve good learning achievement a person must be able to read well and get used to reading.

And for students as agents of change they have new power for this nation. His ideas, concepts and thoughts can change the conditions of the leadership crisis. Students have the capabilities striking if it is developed well and neatly, also supported by an adequate environment. This ability is not only in the intellectual aspect, but includes emotional and spiritual aspects. To support all this, students must have clear goals and targets. The saying goes, to rule the world, start reading. This implies that there is nothing in this world

that deserves to be called "stupid". What about people whose quality of knowledge is low, are they stupid? The answer is of course no, he can only be called a lazy person, especially lazy about reading.

Reading is something that liberates, liberates, and allows a person to fly in the imagination to places he may not be able to visit in his lifetime, and makes it possible to get to know ordinary and extraordinary people from all generations without directly having to shake hands. Doman (1991) in his book *How to Teach Your Baby to Read* states that reading is one of the most important functions in life, that all learning processes are based on the ability to read.

Setiyadi & Sarinah (2019) stated that student academic achievement is the result of an assessment of the learning activities that have been carried out and is a form of final formulation given by the lecturer to see to what extent the student's abilities are expressed in the form of symbols, numbers, letters or sentences that can reflect results that have been achieved. One of the important factors that influences learning achievement is interest in reading, namely a strong desire accompanied by a person's efforts to read. A person who has a strong interest in reading will be manifested in his willingness to obtain reading material and then read it on his own behalf. Because no learning can be done without reading.

For this reason, reading is the main support in learning, as explained by Widodo (2016) stating that learning will be more effective if carried out with reading activities, through reading a person can broaden insight and information. Reading activities are related to the elements of observing, remembering, understanding, comparing, classifying and assessing various information contained in a reading. Lack of reading activities will also have an impact on students' low ability to understand lecture material.

THEORETICAL REVIEW

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METHODOLOGY

Based on the facts explained above, there is a very lack of interest in reading among students, especially university students. Even though reading will influence thinking patterns, the scope of learning activities in college is wider and deeper than studying at previous schools. Of course this will affect academic achievement.

Therefore, the problem formulation in this research is to find out what influence reading interest has on student academic achievement. With the aim of knowing the effect of reading interest on student academic achievement. Data was collected by studying several related theories.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Interest in Reading and Academic Achievement

Syah (2004) states that interest means a high tendency and enthusiasm or a great desire for something. Interests understood and used by people during this time can influence the quality of student learning achievement. In this case, of course, someone who is interested in a field will find it easier to learn about that field. Even if someone is able to learn something, if they don't have interest they won't be able to participate in the learning process. Children's interests can arise from various sources, including instinctive development, intellectual functions, environmental influences, experience, habits and education.

Therefore, a person's interest must be nurtured and directed in order to achieve the desired goals, especially in learning. Interest must be realized in the form of various efforts so that the intended goals can be achieved. Furthermore, in general the definition of reading can be concluded that reading is a complex activity that includes physical and mental. Physical activities related to reading are eye movements and visual acuity, mental activities include memory and comprehension. Reading is important for humans.

By reading, a person can stimulate their brain to think creatively and systematically, broaden and enrich their horizons, and form a superior and competitive personality. Interest has a big influence on reading, because if the reading material studied does not match the student's interests, then the student will not read as well as possible because there is no attraction for him. However, if the reading material attracts students' interest, then the reading material will be easier for the students to learn and store so that students can easily rewrite it when they are tested or tested, which ultimately increases students' learning achievement.

According to Sutarsono (2003) a person's interest in something is a person's high inclination, passion or desire for something. Interest is often also called "interest". Interests can be grouped as traits or attitudes that have certain tendencies. Interest can represent actions (represent motivations). Interest cannot be classified as innate but its nature can be cultivated, learned and developed.

Reading is an activity or cognitive process that attempts to find various information contained in writing. This means that reading is a thinking process to understand the content of the text being read. Therefore, reading is not just seeing a collection of letters that have formed words, groups of words,

sentences, paragraphs and discourse. 31 But more than that, reading is an activity of understanding and interpreting symbols or signs or writing that is meaningful so that the message is conveyed. the author can be accepted by readers.

Abdurrahman (2012) also believes that reading is an ability that all children must have because through reading children can learn a lot about various fields of study. Therefore, reading is a skill that must be taught from the time children enter elementary school and learning difficulties must be overcome as soon as possible. Reading ability is the basis for mastering various fields of study.

And according to Badafal (2001), one of the important factors for achieving success in reading and learning is the readiness factor for reading (readiness for reading subject matter). Readiness is a state or condition that can increase reading and learning success. In fostering and developing students' interest in reading, teacher librarians should pay attention to students' readiness.

Interest in reading is the urge to understand word for word and the content contained in the reading text, so that readers can understand the things stated in the reading. Furthermore, Tampulbon, as quoted by Dalman, explained that interest in reading is a person's willingness or desire to recognize letters to grasp the meaning of the writing.

In simple terms, reading interest can be defined as a high inclination towards reading activities, or as a high desire or enthusiasm for reading activities, there is even an opinion that states that reading interest can be identified with the love for reading.

And Sobur (2006) states that academic achievement is a change in behavioral skills, or abilities that can increase over time and is not caused by a growth process, but by a learning process. The form of the results of the learning process can be in the form of oral or written solutions, and skills and direct problem solving which are measured or assessed using standardized tests.

Academic achievement is evidence of improvement or achievement obtained by someone as a sign of progress or success in their educational program. Student academic achievement is one of the important factors that supports student success in the future.

The Relationship between Reading Interest and Academic Achievement

Buyamin (2013) stated that attitudes, interests and motivation are internal psychological factors that play a very important role in the learning process. Attitude is defined as a tendency to react to something, person or object with like, dislike or indifference. This interest is related to feelings, especially feelings of happiness, therefore it can be said that interest occurs because of an attitude of being happy about something. People who are interested in something mean that they are happy about that something.

One of the attitudes and interests that must exist in learning is that if there is no interest in the lesson or the teacher, then at least the student must

have a positive (accepting) attitude towards the lesson being studied or the teacher. Attitudes and interests as psychological factors have different roles in learning.

As Sabiri (2020) argues, in the learning process attitude functions as a "Dynamic Force", namely as a force that will move people to learn. So students who have a negative attitude (reject or are not happy) towards the lesson or the teacher will not be moved to want to learn. On the other hand, students who have a positive attitude will be moved by their attitude to learning. The role of interest in learning is greater or stronger than attitude. Interest will act as a "Motivating Force", namely as a force that will encourage students to learn. Students who are interested (happy attitude) to the lesson you will appear to be continuously motivated to study diligently, in contrast to students whose attitude is only to accept the lesson, they are only motivated to want to learn but find it difficult to continue to be diligent because there is no incentive.

A child's lack of interest in a lesson will result in learning difficulties. Learning that has no interest may not be in accordance with one's talents, not in accordance with one's needs, not in accordance with one's abilities. Having an interest in the object being studied will encourage people to learn something and achieve maximum learning results. Because interest is a psychological component that plays a role in encouraging a person to achieve the desired goal, so that he is willing to carry out activities around the object being observed.

Reading Interest for Students

According to Kusumawardani (2003), reading activities are the same as building a culture of learning society, which is always thirsty for knowledge. This is part of the self-development process that must always be honed because interest in reading is not acquired from birth. Currently, the cause of students' low absorption of material provided by teachers or lecturers does not only come from potential factors, but can also be caused by students' low book reading habits.

Students who spend more time reading will achieve superior learning achievements compared to those who don't. Having a person's high level of interest will make them more enthusiastic about learning. Someone who has no interest in learning something will usually find it difficult to properly understand the knowledge they are studying, because they are not motivated or have the enthusiasm to be able to master what they have learned.

Interest in reading has a very big influence on students' reading habits. Because if students read without having a high interest in something they want to read, then the student will not read wholeheartedly and as a result he will not be able to fully understand what he has read. Students who are interested in reading activities will understand the importance of reading in their lives so that they are more motivated to excel and achieve in learning, because one way of learning is through reading activities.

Low interest in reading among students will cause a decrease in the ability to think, work, be passive, and play a less active role in learning so that

the academic achievements achieved will also be less. Apart from that, the low interest in reading among students also results in a lack of ideas for creative and innovative arguments during assignment presentations. Because if the interest in reading is high, then of course the students produced will be creative, intelligent and critical students.

Factors Influencing Reading Interest and Academic Achievement

a) Interest in Reading

Then (2019) explains that there are three factors that influence a person's interest, including:

- 1) The inner urge factor (push factor from within). In this case, a person's interest will grow if there is encouragement from within himself (internal), not encouragement from the environment or other people (external).
- 2) The factor of social motivation (social motive factor) Social motives can be a factor that arouses a person's interest in carrying out certain activities, due to the desire to get attention or appreciation from other people and society.
- 3) Emotional factors (emotional factors) Interest is closely related to emotions. If someone finds themselves in positive emotions then carrying out the activity will create a feeling of joy in them, this is what will strengthen their interest in the activity, conversely if someone is in negative emotions it will diminish their interest in it.

b) Academic achievement

The following are several factors that can influence student academic achievement according to Legowo (2016), namely:

- 1) Length of study or the number of hours a student studies while at university level. A student's length of study is an internal factor, namely a factor that originates from within the student, which includes the time spent studying on campus, doing coursework, group discussions with other students, internet access to find sources of knowledge and reading books in the library.
- 2) Motivation to learn. Learning motivation is the overall driving force within the student himself which gives rise to learning activities and provides direction to learning activities. Students who have motivation without being stimulated from outside, in their learning process will tend to be ready and diligent in carrying out learning tasks because they feel the need and want to achieve the real learning goals.
- 3) Family environment. The family environment is the first environment that has the strongest influence on an individual compared to the secondary environment. The family environment includes external factors, namely factors that originate from outside the student. Environmental factors in the family that can influence learning achievement are, parents' parenting style, home atmosphere, family economic conditions, parental attention, and relationships between family members.

- 4) Quality of teaching. Teaching quality is the quality of teachers and facilities in the teaching and learning process. Teaching quality includes external factors. Higher education is one of the educational factors that greatly influences the formation of students' thinking patterns, attitudes, personalities and behavior, because it will also provide color in the form of student identity in the future. The better the lecturer's mastery in using methods, media approaches and teaching principles, the more positive the influence on student academic achievement.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Interest in reading is the urge to understand word for word and the content contained in the reading text, so that readers can understand the things stated in the reading. Furthermore, reading interest is a person's willingness or desire to recognize letters to capture the meaning of the writing.

Academic achievement is evidence of improvement or achievement obtained by someone as a sign of progress or success in their educational program. Student academic achievement is one of the important factors that supports student success in the future.

Interest makes someone motivated to do something that has an impact on their life. This is an important foundation in achieving success. Based on the results of field observations, it was found that the lack of interest in reading among students was caused by a lack of enthusiasm and motivation to visit reading places such as libraries.

An interest in reading is very necessary for all students, because apart from broadening their knowledge, reading also has a big influence on achieving success in their education. As times progress and global competition, if it is not balanced with adequate or adequate human resources, it will cause us to lag behind other countries. Students who lack insight and knowledge will not be able to overcome all kinds of social, political, economic, cultural and other problems that exist in our country.

Low interest in reading among students will cause a decrease in the ability to think, work, be passive, and play a less active role in learning so that the academic achievements achieved will also be less. Apart from that, the low interest in reading among students also results in a lack of ideas for creative and innovative arguments during assignment presentations. Because if the interest in reading is high, then of course the students produced will be creative, intelligent and critical students.

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